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THE ECO MINDSET- DRIVING SUSTAINABLE CHANGE THROUGH GREEN BUSINESS PRACTICES IN TEXTILE SECTOR

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Abstract

The increased emphasis on business sustainability and expanding consumer environmental awareness have driven international companies to embrace environmentally responsible practices. Despite using numerous recycling processes, the textile sector is still confronting issues such as major water contamination, high emissions, and an increased carbon footprint. As a result, there is a growing need for creating green products and using sustainable resources. However, scholars continue to disagree on the determinants and results of industry innovation. In this scenario, the present investigation seeks to investigate the influence of environmental consciousness among clients on the sustainability and efficiency of the fabric sector. The suggested model involves adaptation to a sustainable culture, inventiveness, green effectiveness, and staff commitment. A structured survey was used for gathering data from 198 workers at textile-making organizations. Using a structural equation modelling (SEM) approach, it was shown that an especially significant element for development is adaptation to a green culture, with environmental performance identified as the major consequence. Furthermore, employee dedication is an important mediator linking Performance in the environment and invention. Managers in the textile industry can benefit from the investigations findings. develop a green culture by linking it to green productivity and creativity, both of which can be achieved by raising employee environmental awareness. This, in turn, will help the textile sector reduce emissions.

Keywords: Empirical analysis, business strategy, environmental sensitivity, innovation, green performance, and adaptability

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1. INTRODUCTION

Millions of individuals have been able to leave poverty thanks to growing countries' (EM) capacity for economic progress. However, it has contributed to significant environmental degradation and diminishing resources (OECD, 2017). Because of their heavy reliance on natural resources and susceptibility to changes in the climate, EMs' potential for sustainable growth in GDP is threatened. EMs have major environmental challenges such as groundwater depletion, poor air quality, and a shortage of hygienic landfills for waste disposal (EMS, 2017). Certain industries, such as the textile industry—particularly fast fashion and low-cost, pollutant-laden textiles—significantly contribute to the carbon footprint. India and China are the world's largest cotton growers and exporters, and the Asia-Pacific area accounts for roughly half of the worldwide textile sector.

Water is used extensively in the textile industry throughout all stages of production. Containing hazardous compounds, minerals, pigments, and liquids are sewage from textile manufacture (Bento et al., 2019; Samanta et al., 2019; Saxena et al., 2017). The clothing sector is one of the sectors most damaging at present accounting for around 5% of world emissions (Bauck, 2017). Climate change and environmental restrictions have driven firms to adopt eco-friendly practices. Organizations in emerging markets confront problems in ensuring corporate ethical behavior because they must combine their ecological duties with their business goals (Gupta et al., 2018), while also efficiently utilizing their human resources. Given India's excessive water consumption, regulatory organizations have enforced rules for treating waste water and emissions. As a result, businesses are being encouraged to use more sustainable alternatives, such as zero liquid discharge and water recycling. To be competitive in emerging markets, organizations must constantly innovate and create new tactics. Global biomedical giant General Electric is a corporation headquartered in the United States, employs a variety of techniques, including producing diagnostic software and other components in other countries. Despite initial failures in Chile and Argentina, it successfully entered the Mexican market through a greenfield approach and is now exploring additional emerging markets. Thus, innovation is critical, whether it includes company concepts,

goods, or procedures. As a result, businesses are being encouraged to use more sustainable alternatives, such as zero liquid discharge and water recycling. To be competitive in emerging markets, organizations must constantly innovate and create new tactics. For example, General Electric Healthcare, a multinational corporation headquartered in the United States, employs a variety of techniques, including producing diagnostic software in India and components in China, Hungary, and Mexico. Another example is Home Depot, based in Georgia, USA, which used a variety of marketing methods. Despite initial failures in Chile and Argentina, it successfully entered the Mexican market through a greenfield approach and is now exploring additional emerging markets. Thus, innovation is critical, whether it includes company concepts, goods, or procedures. The innovation literature is divided into two categories: (1) studies that focus on the innovation process and (2) research that investigate the link between innovation and policy. In light of Understanding ecology and the effects of global global warming, creating items free of harmful and poisonous ingredients has become critical for businesses. Thus, green innovation has emerged as an important and necessary component for organisations). Calza et describe technology as industries implementing creative methods to convert their current activities into long-term ones. According to Chen (2008), green innovation may be categorised as management, process, or product innovation.

Developing goods versus procedure or innovation in management since our knowledge of the elements that drive brand innovation and its consequences is weak (Kurkio et al., 2011). As a result, understanding the causes and effect creativity is critical. Green culture characterised a common underlying attitudes regarding environmental management and associated concerns Schein (2010); Marshall et al., 2015). actions of individuals are influenced by these opinions or viewpoints towards handling the environment, and studies have shown that green culture fosters green innovation (Chang, 2015). Moreover, companies have an atmosphere of adaptability are inclined to take risks, profit from their errors, and have the skills and background needed to implement change (Denison, 2000; Senge, 1990). These kinds of companies are able to change with the market (Eisenhardt and Martin, 2000). Thus, it might be argued that company

culture fosters invention and creativity (Martin and Terblanche, 2003), which both have the potential to enhance success (Danneels, 2002), especially environmentally friendly results.

Human resource management it influences organisational working with workers organisational commitment, since dedicated workers put in greater effort at work. Green HRM (GHRM) is a strategy in which organizations apply HRM policies that support sustainable resource usage and environmental causes while increasing employee morale and satisfaction. Furthermore, employees are becoming more dedicated to and happy with organizations that actively promote environmental activities (Ahmmad, 2015). The counteract deterioration waste, state legislation highlight the necessity of technology efforts. (Rahmaan et al.,2020).(Mooktadir et al. 2019) found numerous essential variables for implementing GHRM practices, including a green organisational culture and senior management commitment.(Kumar ,2020) also discovered that upper management involvement was responsible for the second-biggest impact on behaviour, behind company culture. More creative workplace conduct is a result of enhanced organisational engagement at all levels and particularly managers , employees on the front lines, according to Ng et al. (2010). Nevertheless, there is a dearth of empirical study on the topic, especially in Asian contexts (Jafri, 2010; Nguyen et al., 2019). Therefore, it's essential to know how employee involvement contributes to innovation. The following research issues will be addressed by

this project: What are the main forces behind innovation in the textile sector? What are the principal consequences of invention in the cotton sector?

3) How does staff dedication affect inventiveness?

The development of green goods have been found to need green skills the author's name et al., 2012). This study focusses only on internal organisational factors, highlighting factors within the company like employees devotion and the adoption of sustainable practices inside the organisation. Previous studies has looked at both inside and outside organisational elements. Environmental product production has been found to be significantly influenced by corporate sustainability ethics and culture (Keskin et al., 2013; Chen et al., 2012; Dangelico and Pujari, 2010). Organisations that cultivate an adaptability culture are better equipped to handle changes in

their outside world and may undergo internal transformation (Denison and Mishra, 1995). This, in turn, can lead to organisational innovation (Daft, 2007), and this is essential for the success of the company (Danneels, 2002; Cooper while Kleinschmidt Research indicates that since environmental consciousness and sustainable development are closely related, any rise in one has an effect on the other. Additionally, by establishing clear ethical norms, guidelines, and goals, corporate cultures that encourage environmentally conscious behaviour throughout the entire organisation support environmentally friendly innovations (Dangelico 2016). Thus, this study emphasizes environmental success as a consequence of creativity and the adaptability of a green culture as a basic precondition. Drawing on extant literature, the investigation has delineated the subsequent goals:

- To look at the connection between creative and an understanding of adaptability.
- To look at the connection among sustainable efficiency and creativity.
- To look at how employee engagement mediates the relationship between innovation and green performance.

The first section includes a review of the literature and a description of the study's hypotheses. This is followed by an explanation of the research process and analysis. The debate and consequences are covered in the part that follows, which includes both theoretical and practical contributions as well as management implications. The last part presents the conclusion, discusses limits, and makes recommendations for further study.

1. LITERATURE REVIEW

Chang (2011) notes that the two basic environmentally pressures—consumer sustainability and green legislation—are transforming competitiveness in industries. Organisations are therefore compelled to modify their practices, offerings, and sometimes company structures. According to Albort-Morant et al. (2017) and a study by Gun and Spalanzani (2012), sustainability innovation is a means of developing green items and procedures through corporate procedures such employing more or cleaner components in order to minimise emissions and water usage. Howard-Grenville (2006) asserts that

leading people and businesses through a green organisational culture is essential to achieving the effective adoption of green innovation. Green organisational culture, according to Harris and Crane (2002), is an amalgamation of concepts, values, characters, etc traditions beneath a business that show a dedication to operating in an ecologically. A organisation whose personnel prioritise environmental advantages over profit-driven reasons and promote measures. It is still unknown whether specific forms of culture are most successful at encouraging innovation and influencing employee behaviour. Several research have looked into how innovation improves organisational effectiveness (Koac and Ceylan 2007). However, despite the breadth of innovation literature, there is a dearth of emphasis on green invention (Gürlek and Tuina, 2017). While there is study on green innovation in Western service and industrial industries, there is little emphasis paid to green innovation in India's textile industry. This study seeks to fill this vacuum by investigating the causes and effects of inventiveness, as highlighted by Crossa to Apaydin (2010), who assert that assessing the connections across creation forces and the implications is necessary to advance the study of innovation. Consequently, this appraisal of literature looks at three main areas: the connection involving discovery and green effectiveness, the function that organisational loyalty plays as a mediator, and the connections amongst flexible culture and development.

1.1. Development of the Conceptual Framework and Hypotheses

2.1.1: Flexibility Innovation & Culture

The term "adaptive culture" refers to a set of cultural characteristics that enable an organisation to better respond to environmental changes, "anticipate and adjust to shifts in the environment." Adaptability is recognised as a critical characteristic for organisational competitiveness and sustainability is to green invention grown in recent years (Dangelico, 2016). As social and political constraints mount, organisations are increasingly creating settings that promote adaptation and contribute to the creative goods (Song, 2020). According to Wodman, 1993, an adaptable organisational culture may foster innovation, while Herbig and Dunphy (1998) argue that an organization's culture is crucial to the performance of innovation. According to

Denison and Mishra (1995), organisations that possess an adaptable culture are more capable of implementing internal changes in reaction to external circumstances. Employee innovation skills are fostered and influenced by a supportive work environment or culture. Companies that are dedicated to ongoing innovation and knowledge development can improve performance, with new product development serving as a crucial prelude to improved organisational performance (Chan et al., 2017). Three primary elements affect the adaption to green culture: external (competition, market trends, rules, and regulations), internal (systems and performance), and management (strategic policies and attitude) (Law and Gunasekaran, 2012). The degree to which an organisation adapts to sustainable development depends on the different effects of various components inside the organization. As a result, we suggest:

H1. There is a connection between innovation and an adaptable culture.

1.1.2. Green Performance and Innovation

According to Zhu and Sarkis (2004), implementing green practices is expected to enhance environmental or the performances. Green's sales, stated by Olsthoorn et al. (2001), is a measure of a company's environmental interactions. Innovative product design is the process of developing new ideas or modifying already-existing items or services (The practice and Ahmed, 2006). Speed and inventiveness have been linked in previous investigations (Danneels, 2002; Cooper and Kleinschmidt, 1995; Brown and Eisenhardt, 1995). These results demonstrate how crucial development is to improving company performance. empirical studies on environmentally friendly innovations, notably highlights productivity as a crucial outcome, particularly in the domains of sustainable development and total company performance (Zhang et al., 2019; Tang et al., 2018; Handayani), provides more proof for this. (Singh et al., 2020; Huang and Li, 2017; Kucukoglu and Pinar, 2015; Weng et al., 2015; Alhadid and As'Ad, 2014; Chiou et al., 2011; Kucukoglu and Pinar, 2015; Singh et al., 2020; Huang and Li, 2017; Weng et al., 2015). Additionally, studies have linked environmentally friendly innovations with profitability (Carrion-Flores and Innes, 2010), sustainable development initiatives and market outcomes (Pujari, 2006), and environmentally friendly innovation and business outcome (Gluch et al., 2009). Given this

discussion, we hypothesise that: (Carrion-Flores and Innes, 2010). In light of this conversation, we speculate that:

H2: Green performance and innovation (green goods) are correlated.

1.1.3. Commitment's Mediating Role

The drive to behave in a way that is advantageous to the company is referred to as employee commitment. Although there has been much study in this field, Polonsky was the first to examine how it applied to environmental sustainability in 1998. This environmental approach has garnered attention lately. We primarily look at emotional commitment among workers in this study. Employee dedication is frequently correlated with the effectiveness of their innovation initiatives (Youndt et al., 1996). Reduced turnover is positively correlated with employee commitment (Steers, 1977). Less dedicated workers typically just complete the bare minimum of duties (Ricketta, 2002). On the other hand, workers who are happy to be employed by the company could go above and beyond the call of duty, exhibiting a great degree of dedication and devotion which therefore improves performance (Jaworski and Kohli, 1993; Allen and Shanock, 2013). Concern for and interest in the organization's environmental goals are related to an employee's commitment to environmental concerns (Paille and Valeau, 2020). Thus, with committed staff, attaining organisational green goals is possible. Increased productivity and better organisational performance have been associated with higher levels of staff commitment (Arthur, 1994; Owens, 2006). Moreover, employee dedication can be positively impacted by top management's attention to environmental concerns (Aguinis and Glavas, 2012). All things considered, staff dedication to change—in this example, embracing green practices—is essential to an organization's operational procedures and its capacity to develop novel goods that satisfy consumer and environmental demands (Hasu et al., 2014).

When workers are committed to change, their perspectives improve we suggest:

H3. The connection between innovation and green performance is mediated by employee commitment.

H3a. There is a connection between employee dedication and creativity.

H3b. There is a connection between green performance and staff commitment.

2. METHODS OF RESEARCH

Fig. 2 shows the research approach framework for this study. The first steps in the process were defining the issue and studying the pertinent literature, which included the textile industry's dedication, innovation, culture of flexibility, and green performance (as described in Sections 1, 2, and 3). Then, information was gathered from middle-level workers at Indian textile manufacturing companies using a standardized questionnaire.

The model evaluation was carried out once the data was collected. Through exploratory component analysis, the measurement model's one-dimensionality was confirmed. Internal consistency dependability was assessed using Cronbach's alpha and composite reliability. Indicator reliability was examined using indicated vehicles. The convergent validity was estimated using Average Variance Extracted (AVE), while discriminant reliability was evaluated using cross-loaded loadings. The Fornell-Larcker and the HTMT0.85 criteria. Additionally, indicator validity was confirmed with marker loads and the variable inflation factor (VIF), when reliability of constructs was assessed with inside concept connections. The structure-based model's validity was evaluated using the coefficient de predictability (R^2), path coefficients, T-values, effect size (f^2), predictive relevance (Q^2), goodness of fit index, and standardised root mean square residual. The model's validation was followed by a presentation and interpretation of the hypothesis testing findings.

2.1. Design of the Questionnaire

Data were gathered using a survey using paper and pencil, and a structured questionnaire created. There are two sections to the questionnaire: A and B. Respondents are asked to provide demographic details in Section A, such as age, gender, and educational background. Items about the study's analysed constructs are included in Section B. Pilot research needs a minimum sample size of thirty, according to Browne (1995). To improve the questionnaire, 37 participants, including academics and professionals from the business, participated in pilot research. Before the primary data collecting questionnaire was finalized, the appropriate

language tweaks and alterations were done based on input.

2.2. Measurement and Variables

Green Performance is the variable in question in the current investigation, and it is measured using a Yu et al. (2017) nine-item scale (for example, "Our firm meets the energy input requirements"). Ability A trio of queries from previous research (Denison and Mishra, 1995; Lau with Ngo, 2004) was employed for evaluating culture (for example, "whether the culture of this business should be labelled flexible"). Chang (2019), Chen (2008), and

2.3. Data and sample gathering

The National Capital Region (NCR) of Delhi's textile manufacturing companies received the questionnaire. Each organization's representative received two surveys.

Chen et al. (2006) developed a three-item scale to assess innovative products, particularly innovations related to green products (for example, "The organisation uses low-pollution substances in the creation of goods, design, which is or implementation"). Human loyalty to sustainability is assessed using a three-item modified Raineri and Paille (2016) test (for example, "I care approximately our company's sustainability concerns"). Every single thing has been rated.

Figure 1: displays the theoretical basis for the research as well as the relationships between employee commitment, product innovation, adaptable culture, and ecological performance.

Since it was difficult for the researcher to approach the senior management, snowball sampling (Johnson, 2014) was utilized to collect data between August 2019 and January 2020. 215 questionnaires in all were gathered, yielding a 53.75% response rate. Only 198 of the 215 surveys were used for additional analysis since the respondents did not supply enough information. 198 is an appropriate sample size for the current investigation, according to the minimal sample size estimate approach "10 times rule" in PLS-SEM .

Table 1: Details of the responders are displayed

Age	Less than 25	2.50E+36	3.50E+46	More than 45
	42 (21%)	82 (42%)	62 (31%)	12 (6%)
Gender	Male	Female		
	132 (67%)	66 (33%)		
Education qualification	High School	Graduation	Post-Graduation	PhD
	21 (11%)	97 (49%)		9 (4%)
Managerial Level	Executives	Middle-Level Managers		Senior Level Managers
	25 (12%)	111 (56%)	71 (36%)	62 (32%)

Fig. 2: Framework of Research

3. ANALYSIS

PLS-SEM is frequently used for evaluating research models in their early phases, especially when they have not been well investigated (Zhu et al., 2012). It is especially well-suited for small sample sizes (Agarwal and Karahanna, 2000). As a result, the study used this methodology. Tables 2 and 3 provide specific valid and reliable of the model. Composite reliability values need to be at least .7 considered reliable (Haire , 2014). The composite values for commitment, green performance, adaptable culture, and innovation are shown in Table 2 at 0.88, 0.93, and 0.83, respectively. These values indicate good internal consistency dependability for all variables every value above 0.70. The average extracted variance (AVE) was

employed to determine the validity of convergent. Commitment has an AVE rating of 0.72, green performance is 0.65, adaptable culture is 0.88, and innovation is 0.75. According to all values more than .5, indicating strong convergent value. The Fornell-Larcker criterion, which states that the product of the square roots of the average variance AVE for every principle (such as 0.93 for adaptive culture) exceeds the association within the parts, was used to assess the discriminant validity. Further establishing validity of discrimination, all Heterotrait-Monotrait Ratio (HTMT) values were below the 0.85 limit (Henseler et al., 2014). HTMT.85 criteria.

Figure 3: shows the PLS SEM findings (ADC = Adaptability Culture, INN = Product Innovation, COM = Employee Commitment, and PERF = Green Performance)

Construct	Adaptability Culture	Commitment	Innovation	Green Performance
Adaptability Culture	0.938			
Commitment	-0.058	0.85		
Innovation	-0.207	0.32	0.866	
Green Performance	-0.078	0.458	0.401	0.809

Table 2: shows the Fornell-Larcker criterion for discriminant validity.

3.1. Assessment of structural models

The variance inflation factor (VIF) values were obtained to assess collinearity. Hair et al. (2019) advocate a VIF value of fewer than 3. Table 4 demonstrates each of the parameters used corresponding to the extrinsic domain were beneath 3, showing that there is no need to be concerned about collinearity issues. When it was found that the variables had a direct link, a facilitator was added to the model. The bootstrapping process (5000 sub samples) was used to assess the significance of the outer loading of the hypotheses being considered.

Variables	Adaptability Culture	Commitment	Innovation	Green Performance
Adaptability Culture			1	1.114
Commitment				
Innovation				
Green Performance		1		1.114

Table 4: Inflation factor variance

4. ANALYSIS

The factor loadings were significant ($p < 0.001$) and more than 0.7. We used both procedural and statistical remedies, as described by Podsakoff et al. (2012), which widespread reported survey. Answer confidentially, data were gathered for procedural measures from a number of sources as opposed to just one, and the item order was changed. To make sure CMB had no impact on the data, further tests were performed, including the common latent factor (CLF $< 50\%$) and Harman's single factor test ($< 50\%$). Following the use of these protocols, 198 respondents' data were used. Table 5 shows that the structural model linkages are statistically significant based on the coefficients for both direct and indirect pathways. For commitment, the R2 values .103, for invention, they are .043, and for green performances, they are .282. Gao et al. (2020) classify R2 values as follows: 0.02 represents modest effects, 0.13 represents moderate effects, and 0.26 represents substantial impacts. According to Ritchey (2008), in the social sciences, R2 values between 0.2 and 0.49 are considered fairly high, whereas those between 0.04 and 0.16 are considered moderately weak. These criteria indicate that dedication and innovation have fairly modest influence on the model. Validating the model-data fit, the green performance R2 of 0.282 shows that staff dedication, green product innovation, and

adaptable culture.

Tables 5 and 6 provide the route coefficients and outcomes of the hypothesis tests, confirming hypothesis 1. Validating hypothesis 2, the route coefficient for innovation to green performance (INN / PERF) is 4.55 a p value of 0. With a p value of .01 an indirect route coefficient of 2.536 for innovation to green performance through commitment (INN / COM / PERF), hypothesis 3 about the mediating function of commitment is confirmed. Using blindfolding techniques (Tenenhaus et al., 2005), the cross-validated redundancy Q² was determined. For green performance, it was 0.175

Path	t - value	p - value
ADC / INN	3.0	0.003
COM / PERF	5.9	0
INN / COM	3.4	0.001
INN / PERF	4.9	0
INN / COM / PERF	2.5	0.01

Table 5: Path coefficients

Hypothesis	Path	p - values	Decision
Hypothesis 1	ADC / INN	0.003	ACCEPTED
Hypothesis 2	INN / PERF	0	ACCEPTED
Hypothesis 3	INN / COM / PERF	0.011	ACCEPTED
H3a	INN / COM	0.001	ACCEPTED
H3b	INN / PERF	0	ACCEPTED

Table 6: Hypothesis Test

Heseler and colleagues, 2016). Effect sizes were evaluated using Cohen's Z 2 f 2 method, where small, medium, and high effect sizes are represented by $Z 2 \geq 0.02$ f 2 ≥ 0.02 , $Z 2 \geq 0.15$ f 2 ≥ 0.15 , and $Z 2 \geq 0.35$ f 2 ≥ 0.35 (Cohen, 1988). This metric assesses how an independent variable affects a dependent variable. Within this framework, green performance is significantly impacted by staff dedication.

4. DECISION AND IMPLICATIONS

Textile industry organisations that promote an adaptive culture or can make adjustments for changes in the environment should prioritise innovation. Furthermore, hypothesis H3 is supported by the fact that staff dedication product innovation performance. Green Human Resource

Management (GHRM), which incorporates techniques for environmental conservation and preservation, was developed in response to the growing demand. Including environmental goals into organisational aims and plans improves the company's reputation while also increasing its efficiency.

This study focusses on GHRM studies within a setting of India, a developing country, to investigate how employee commitment might help organisations perform better. Compared to non-eco-friendly alternatives, adopting eco-friendly methods is sometimes more costly and labour-intensive (Ohtomo & Hirose, 2007). Top the company's environmental actions have the potential to impact staff engagement and behaviour. According to a crucial success metric for manufacturing that is environmentally sensitive is the dedication of upper management. Green policies and practices may help companies raise consciousness among workers. By providing incentives and remuneration containers, employers can encourage staff members to consistently use these techniques and meet environmental targets (Govindarajulu and Daily, 2004).

Additionally, a flexible organisational culture may support businesses in recognising, evaluating, and utilising adaptable qualities that support competitive survival. Despite the fact that adaptive culture has been found to be a substantial forerunner to textile manufacturing enterprises may be low or insufficient. There are a number of possible causes for this problem. An ASSOCHAM (2015) research states that India is slowing down its adoption of new technologies and that this is leading to a need for more skilled labour as a result of these advancements. Despite the availability of government programs like the Technology Upgradation Fund Scheme, this has resulted in a reluctance to accept new technology, with a projected 26.2 million competent personnel lacking by 2022. Organisations employ manual machine due to outage incur higher expenses. Moreover, the motivation additional innovation research and development is reduced if rivals may copy innovations at cheaper prices. These elements might account for the lack of innovation or delay impacting businesses' green performance. It should be mentioned, nevertheless, that certain Indian businesses, such as Century Rayon, have embraced global sustainable manufacturing standards. One example of this is the Sustainable Textile Production (STeP) certification that OEKOTEX

awarded in 2014, signifying an open and honest commitment to sustainable production.

4.1. Consequences for Theory and Practice of Sustainable Development and Cleaner Production

5.1.1. Conceptual Consequences

The importance of organisational culture in fostering creativity has been emphasised by earlier models of the innovation process, including those put out by Hauser (1998), West and Farr (1990), and (Woodman1993) (Gudmundson, 2013). Additionally, it has been demonstrated organisational is influenced by cultural adaptation (Kanter, 2000). Nevertheless, it is unclear whether particular elements of corporate culture are best for encouraging innovation, and these elements haven't been put to the test empirically. Given the importance of innovation in the textiles sector, our research tackles questions about the origins and consequences of innovation in this field. Also given that there has been not much existing research on the subject, this research project contributes to the corpus of understanding on ecological sales, particularly as it pertains to employee engagement and an adaptable culture (Wang, 2019; Zhang et al., 2019). More sales may result from educating and informing customers about green products and the advantages they offer society (Tandon et al., 2020). Campaigns to raise public knowledge of different certifications might be useful in fostering customer trust about the authenticity of products. These campaigns' increased consumer education has the ability to change non-buyers' behaviour and intentions towards ethical purchase with those who care more about the environment having a higher propensity to buy green items.

5.1.2. Consequences for Management

The study's conclusions provide insightful management guidance to companies looking to improve their environmental sustainability. Numerous environmental management systems can help businesses operate more sustainably, however many businesses may not be able to afford or adopt these systems due to their high implementation costs. Consequently, alternative strategies that improve environmental sustainability and boost green performance include encouraging a flexible organisational culture and changing employee

behaviour to strengthen environmental commitment. Our results, which emphasise the vital role that employee engagement plays in fostering innovation and improving green performance, corroborate this. Employers may take advantage of this by creating training curricula and green HR policies that encourage staff members' dedication to ecologically friendly . who found that green performance is positively impacted by green innovation. In light of these findings, we advise industry managers to foster an adaptable culture improves the of green products, which will improve green performance. By establishing clear green goals for staff members, rewarding environmentally friendly behaviour, and putting green HRM policies and procedures into place, managers may help to cultivate this culture.

Enhancing green product innovation may also provide businesses a competitive edge, which is essential for prospering in the global marketplace (Chang, 2011). Future innovation is expected to come from organisations that provide a supportive environment and culture, whereas an unfavourable culture might stifle creativity. Results indicate encouraging innovation via the development of an adaptable culture. Indian textiles sector can adjust to changes in the environment and reinvent its processes and products more quickly if it cultivates a strong adaptable culture. For example, the textile sector had many difficulties during the COVID-19 outbreak and the statewide shutdown. In response to consumer demand, they started manufacturing stylish masks and organising exports. But nations like Vietnam and Bangladesh have begun selling similar masks earlier (Times of India, 2020).

The inability of Indian textile enterprises to innovate due to a lack of an adaptable culture is the reason for the delay in their capacity to adjust to environmental developments.

At the moment, modernisation, employment, skill development, investment attractiveness, and technology upgrading are prioritised in Indian government programs and plans. The standardising policies connected to culture be implemented by organisational boards and legislators to improve the efficacy of current programs and projects. In the face of fierce competition from both domestic and international multinational firms, enterprises operating in the Indian textile sector had to concentrate on developing innovative green products and creating industry-specific strategic strategies and roadmaps in order to meet sustainability objectives. Here are some more

suggestions for enhancing the textile industry's green performance: Create a Zero-Waste Action Plan and put solutions into action to reduce waste and increase resource efficiency. Boost Green Commitment at the Top: encourage senior management to improve their commitment to environmental challenges. To encourage recycling and the circular economy, consider the following: panipat, Delhi NCR, and Haryana's small and medium-sized firms (SMEs) gather and recycle used clothing. But the persistent problem of textile dumping need better approaches and a heightened understanding of adaptive culture in these kinds of businesses. Take a cue from Indian start-ups such as Kiabza and Lionise and embrace circular economy ideas in the textile industry. Employ Digitisation solutions: Use blockchain-based solutions such as Trustrace to improve supply chain traceability and transparency. Create New Collection Models: Myntra, a major leader in e-commerce fashion, partners with Goonj, an NGO, to enable online buyers to trade worn clothing, which is then given to people in need, Examine Medical Textiles: Because of the lack of knowledge on medical textiles in India at the moment, particularly in times of emergency such as the COVID-19 epidemic, authorities have pushed for the development of creative and reusable PPE

5. CONCLUSION

Though they frequently struggle with its execution, managers are beginning to recognise the importance of innovation. One of the study's main contributions is the demonstration of how creating an adaptable culture within companies may greatly foster creativity. Beyond analysing innovation in the Indian textile sector, the study also looks at how employee commitment influences the development of an environmentally conscious organisational culture. This work fills a significant vacuum in the body of knowledge about innovation in this industry. The research model delves into the factors that influence innovation as well as its results, with a particular focus on how employee dedication may improve environmental performance. The study finds that fostering a flexible, environmentally conscious culture in the textile industry will spur internal innovation. Important suggestions include pressuring decision-makers to create regulations that strictly impose restrictions on black markets, assess the usage of current programs, and guarantee a steady supply of electricity to the industry.

LIMITATIONS

Because it is survey-based, this study has many drawbacks is adequately represent the dynamic relationship between employee commitment and organisational flexibility over time. A longer-term investigation could offer a more thorough assessment of these factors. Subsequent investigations may examine supplementary factors, such the level of dedication from upper management, and their influence on the conceptual framework. The correlations in the study model may potentially be influenced by moderating factors. For instance, leadership philosophies and practices like the Toyota Production System's Respect for People may have an impact on worker dedication. Furthermore, research in the future may include new industries or compare different sector more comprehensive results may be obtained by expanding the sample size and incorporating various geographic settings. There may be problems with answer consistency and inter-rater reliability because each firm received two surveys, yet each company usually only received one or two responses.

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